

From Traditional to Digital: Analyzing Information Culture Change and User Satisfaction in Southern Delta University Main Library

Esemena JEROH

*Department of Library and Information Science,
Southern Delta University, Ozoro,
Delta State, Nigeria.*

Abstract

This study examined the relationship between change in information culture and library users' satisfaction in Southern Delta University Main Library, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria. The study employed the descriptive survey research design and sampled 353 registered library users through simple random sampling. Data were collected using a structured, validated questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Spearman Rank Correlation at a 0.05 significance level. Findings indicate that users perceive the library's information culture as highly supportive of digital adoption, with staff openness, management support, and feedback integration contributing to positive experiences. Notably, the correlation analysis revealed a strong positive and statistically significant relationship ($r = 0.9016$, $p < 0.05$) between change in information culture and user satisfaction. This suggests that proactive information management, digital resource promotion, and responsiveness to user feedback significantly enhance satisfaction levels. The study concludes that cultivating a robust and adaptive information culture is pivotal for sustaining user satisfaction in contemporary academic libraries. Implications for library management include prioritizing policies, technological infrastructure, and participatory practices that reinforce an effective and user-centered digital library environment.

Keywords: Information Culture, User Needs, Academic Libraries, Change Management, Users' Satisfaction

Introduction

Universities today operate in an environment where access to reliable, timely and well-managed information is central to teaching, learning, research and community engagement. University libraries are pivotal to this information ecosystem as Ekpang and Ekenge (2021) asserts that they collect, organize and mediate access to information resources and services that underpin academic activity. However, the efficiency of those services is not only dependent on collections or technology, but also influenced by several factors.

Arguably, the increasing advances in digital technologies have reshaped the global information landscape, compelling university libraries to rethink their operational models and strategic orientations. To remain relevant in this rapidly evolving environment, academic libraries not only adopt new technologies, but also develop user-centred strategies capable of meeting the increasingly dynamic expectations of their patrons. As Kaur (2018) observes, the twenty-first century presents unprecedented opportunities that have made library users more informed, more discerning, and more inclined toward specialized and technology-driven services.

Consequent on the above, academic libraries worldwide have experienced significant transformations, by migrating from manual procedures to fully automated systems; thus, altering how information is accessed, stored, organized, and delivered. Notable examples of

transformations in libraries include the migration from traditional card catalogues to Integrated Library Systems (ILS) such as Koha, which enable users to search, borrow, and renew materials online, thereby enhancing efficiency and accessibility (Ocholla & Mokhtar, 2020).

Similarly, service delivery models have expanded in libraries to include personalized virtual reference services, such as live chat and email consultations, which provide timely assistance without requiring physical presence (Kaur, 2018; Adeolu-Akande, & Oyedokun, 2022). These developments reflect a broader movement toward digitalisation and user-centred service innovation, both of which are central to maintaining high levels of user satisfaction in contemporary academic libraries.

By definition, user satisfaction is a widely used outcome measure for library performance. Barfi et al (2023) stated that satisfaction captures patrons' perceptions that services, collections, facilities and staff interactions meet their information needs and support their academic goals. Empirical studies in Nigerian academic environments suggest variation in satisfaction across service dimensions in terms of reference and inter-library loan, physical facilities, e-library/e-resource access), often tied to organizational and cultural factors within libraries (Kalankesh et al. 2020, Moustapha 2021 and Ayuba, 2022). Understanding what drives users' satisfaction is necessary for library managers and university administrators who must prioritize resources and design interventions that raise service quality and institutional reputation.

Noteworthy, the transformations recorded by libraries did not occur in isolation as deliberate and systematic change management are necessary to drive such changes/transformations to be effective. Khan and Kamal (2016) conceptualize change management as a structured approach to transitioning an organisation from its current state to a desired future state. In the broader business environment, change management is recognised as an ongoing process of aligning organisational capabilities with emerging market demands to enhance responsiveness and competitiveness (Nwinyokpugi, 2018). From this perspective, change management entails conscious and systematic efforts to navigate environmental shifts, improve organisational efficiency, and meet stakeholder expectations (Kaur, 2018; Ali & Anwar, 2021; Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2022). These definitions underscore the interconnectedness of organisational transformation, human behaviour, strategic adaptation, and service performance.

Within the library context, change management involves efforts to respond effectively to evolving user demands and the changing information environment (Purushothama, 2015). Adebayo et al. (2018) further describe it as the managerial process through which libraries adapt to the constantly shifting needs and expectations of their users. The mechanisms that drive these transitions are often referred to as change management factors (Sakib, 2022; Khan & Kamal, 2016). These factors play critical roles in facilitating effective organisational transformation, minimising associated risks, and enabling libraries to harness emerging opportunities (Sakib, 2022). They also determine the extent to which libraries can adapt to changes in technology, resources, institutional priorities, and most importantly, user expectations (Aslam, 2022; Trzeciak, 2024). Extant studies have identified several change management factors to include change in information culture, technological change, change in organizational structure and a host of others (Furxhi & Dollija, 2021; Archibong & Ibrahim, 2021; Udo & Edidiong, 2022; Aslam, 2022; Trzeciak, 2024; Anunobi & Jeroh, 2025).

Information culture, as a critical change management factor, plays a central role in shaping how libraries implement digital services and by extension, achieve higher levels of user

satisfaction. According to Gillian (2017), information culture encompasses the norms, values, and behaviours associated with the creation, sharing, and use of information within an organisation. In libraries, it reflects how staff, users, and other stakeholders perceive and engage with information resources, particularly as digital technologies continue to transform information practices (Widén & Karim, 2018).

It is expected that strong information culture may contribute to fostering openness, adaptability, and user engagement in libraries; thus, making both staff and library patrons more receptive to technological changes and innovations (Deja & Wojcik, 2021). Consequently, cultivating a positive information culture may have implication for user experience and the continued relevance and success of academic libraries in the digital era (Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025).

This study therefore examines the transformation of libraries from traditional to digital technologies by focusing specifically on the relationship between change in information culture and user satisfaction of library patrons in Southern Delta University main library, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria. Furtherance of this objective, this study hypothesizes thus:

H₀: Change in information culture do not have significant positive correlation with library users' satisfaction in Southern Delta University main library.

2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1 Information Culture

Information culture in academic libraries refers to the shared values, behaviours, norms, and practices that shape how information is created, managed, disseminated, and used by both library staff and users. It embodies the collective orientation toward information within the library environment, in addition to how information resources are organized, how staff facilitate access, and how users engage with available services. Impliedly, information culture represents a critical dimension of the library's organisational identity and a foundational element in determining how effectively libraries and library management adapts to technological and behavioural changes.

Lauri, Heidmets, and Virkus (2016) conceptualize information culture as the constellation of attitudes, behaviours, and values that influence how individuals select, categorise, communicate, and utilize information. This view underscores its role in shaping everyday information practices. Similarly, Malgorzata (2015) argues that information culture emerges from the sociological observation of ongoing social, economic, and technological transformations. This perspective sees information culture as a concept that is deeply embedded in the realities of a networked society, where new norms, lifestyles, and digital innovations continuously redefine how individuals and institutions interact with information.

Furthermore, Godwin, Madukoma, and Soyemi (2021) describes information culture as a significant aspect in information management while delivering e-library services for user satisfaction. Expanding this discourse, Gillian (2017) describes information culture as the collective and often deeply ingrained practices, values, and norms that guide the creation, sharing, and management of information within an organisation. This definition highlights the dual nature of information culture: it can either enable or constrain information use, depending on the underlying attitudes and values held by staff and users. It involves how individuals, organizations and even libraries perceive, evaluate, and use information. In libraries, this

culture is vital for ensuring that users, staff, and stakeholders engage effectively with information resources as technology advances, user expectations change, and the shift from physical to digital collections (Widén and Karim, 2018).

Accordingly, Deja and Wojcik (2021), avers that information culture frames staff behaviour in areas such as information sharing, records management and innovation in service delivery as well as user expectations and practice. This can either enable or constrain the delivery of high-quality library services to users. The authors further stated that a strong information culture fosters an environment where staff and users are more open to changes.

In the context of libraries therefore, information culture is shaped by the norms governing information management and by the attitudes of the individuals who produce, access, and disseminate information. Empirical insights however reveal that values and attitudes are central to understanding information culture in library environments. Otuza, Akintayo, and Alegbeleye (2021) note that attitudes may manifest in user preferences for particular forms of information or communication channels, while behaviours reflect how individuals navigate and engage with available resources. These dynamics suggest that a robust information culture not only supports effective information flow but also enhances organisational productivity.

Operationally, this study conceptualizes information culture as the attitudes, values, and behavioural orientations that influence how library users access and utilize information resources to meet their academic or informational needs. As university libraries transition from traditional to digital service environments, cultivating a positive and adaptive information culture becomes essential for ensuring efficient service delivery and sustaining user satisfaction. This conceptualization forms the basis for examining how changes in information culture influence user satisfaction within university libraries in South-South Nigeria, with specific attention to the evolving context of Southern Delta University Main Library.

2.2 Users' Satisfaction

Understanding the concept of *users' satisfaction* requires an appreciation of the constituent ideas of “user” and “satisfaction.” A user, in its simplest form, refers to an individual who makes use of a service, item or resource (Oxford English Dictionary, 2001). Within the library context, Lalrokhawma and Verma (2018) describe users as information seekers who engage with one or more library services or resources, regardless of the frequency of use. Satisfaction, on the other hand, denotes the sense of fulfilment or pleasure derived when a desired need or expectation is met (Oxford English Dictionary, 2001). It encapsulates the affective and cognitive responses associated with achieving a valued outcome.

Integrating these concepts, Thereseta (2016) defines users' satisfaction as the evaluative response that arises when users compare perceived service performance with their expectations. This aligns with established satisfaction models which suggest that when perceived performance falls short of expectations, dissatisfaction occurs; when performance matches expectations, users feel satisfied; and when performance exceeds expectations, users experience heightened satisfaction (Kalankesh et al., 2020). Thus, users' satisfaction is fundamentally shaped by the users' internal benchmarks of what a service *should* deliver.

The expectations and perceptions that users bring to their library experience are influenced by several factors, including their immediate information needs, prior interactions with similar

services, and the experiences shared by peers or colleagues (Thereseta, 2016; Adeniran, 2020). These factors shape how users interpret service performance and, ultimately, the level of satisfaction they derive.

Within the library environment, users' satisfaction refers to the extent to which the resources, services, and overall environment meet or surpass users' information needs and expectations. This may include locating precise information, gaining timely assistance, accessing quality resources, or achieving academic or research goals. Umoh and Agwunobi (2020) emphasize that satisfaction is closely linked to the availability, relevance, quality, and adequacy of library resources, facilities, and services.

Users' satisfaction in libraries can therefore be evaluated based on how well the available information resources and services align with and fulfil users' needs. As Adeniran (2020) notes, meeting users' information needs requires not only the provision of appropriate resources but also effective service delivery mechanisms that facilitate meaningful engagement with those resources.

Operationally, this study conceptualizes users' satisfaction as the degree of positive experience or fulfilment that library users derive from accessing and utilizing library resources and services, particularly when these services adequately meet or exceed their expectations. In the contemporary academic environment that is characterized by rapid technological advancements, evolving user demographics, and changing patterns of information consumption, an understanding and improvement of users' satisfaction is integral to sustaining library relevance and enhancing user engagement.

Accordingly, this study seeks to examine change in information culture affect users' satisfaction, with empirical evidence from the Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria.

2.3 Change in Information Culture and Library Users' Satisfaction

Information culture, as a key change management variable, reflects the collective values, attitudes, and behaviours that shape how individuals within an organisation engage with information. In academic libraries, information culture influences users' intentions to access and utilize information resources, thereby contributing significantly to their overall satisfaction (Godwin, Madukoma, & Soyemi, 2021; Adeolu-Akande, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2023). A library's ability to adjust to technological and organisational changes, and the extent to which such changes enhance user experience, are deeply rooted in its prevailing information culture. Information culture is universal, to the extent that every organisation possesses one, regardless of its size, structure, or geographic location (Oliver, 2017). In libraries, a positive and adaptive information culture facilitates the seamless flow of information, enabling users to readily locate, access, and use relevant resources. When users can conveniently obtain high-quality information in a timely manner, their satisfaction tends to increase. Libraries with strong information cultures often exhibit effective communication structures and demonstrate greater adaptability to change, allowing them to offer more responsive and user-focused services. This responsiveness is often reflected in users' perceptions of efficient service delivery, particularly when their inquiries are addressed promptly and accurately.

A proactive information culture is expected to enhance libraries' ability to incorporate new technologies and digital resources, thereby improving users' experiences with modern

information systems (Thirupathi, 2024). Such libraries tend to embrace innovations such as digital catalogues, online databases, and virtual reference tools which enhance service efficiency, transparency, and accessibility. Users generally value these modernized systems because they promote convenience and provide dependable access to information, ultimately strengthening trust in library services (Ugwuanyi et al., 2022).

An essential feature of an effective information culture is its emphasis on continuous learning and feedback. Libraries that actively solicit and integrate user feedback cultivate cultures of participatory decision-making and knowledge exchange (Fourie & Meyer, 2018). In such environments, users feel acknowledged when their suggestions are considered and when visible improvements follow. This responsiveness reinforces users' sense of value and increases their satisfaction, especially as services evolve to better meet their needs.

Overall, changes in information culture directly contribute to user satisfaction by ensuring that technological and service-related innovations are user-oriented, efficiently implemented, and continually refined. When a library fosters a culture that prioritizes accessibility, transparency, adaptability, and user engagement, it creates a more responsive and trustworthy environment. Such an environment enhances users' experiences, thereby strengthening satisfaction and reinforcing the library's role as a modern academic support system.

2.4 Review of Empirical Studies

A considerable body of empirical work has examined the role of information culture in shaping organisational performance, service delivery, and user satisfaction across library and information environments. These studies provide critical insights that inform the present research.

Amjid and Shamshad (2019) investigated how organisational information culture affects lifelong learning among information professionals in university libraries in Pakistan. Using a positivist paradigm and quantitative approach, the study surveyed 226 library and information science (LIS) professionals selected through stratified sampling method. Data were obtained using a carefully structured questionnaire and analysis was done using mean scores and Pearson correlation. Outcomes from the study revealed a positive association between information culture and professionals' lifelong learning behaviours, which further contributed to job satisfaction, organisational learning, and improved service performance. This study shares conceptual similarities with the present research in its focus on information culture and its behavioural outcomes and in its use of questionnaires and correlational analysis. However, it differs significantly with regard to population (LIS professionals rather than library users), geographical context, and research paradigm.

In a related study, Otuza, Akintayo, and Alegbeleye (2021) examined the influence of information culture on job satisfaction among university registry personnel in South-West Nigeria. Employing a descriptive survey design, the study sampled 715 staff using a stratified random technique. Analysis was done using regression analysis and findings showed that specific dimensions of information culture (information sharing, proactiveness, and information control) did not significantly predict job satisfaction individually, although information culture collectively contributed to perceived improvements in service delivery. While the study reinforces the relevance of information culture in shaping work outcomes, its

focus on administrative personnel and service responsiveness contrasts with the current study's emphasis on library users' satisfaction in the Southern Delta University main library.

Godwin, Madukoma, and Soyemi (2021) assessed the influence of information culture and organisational structure on user satisfaction with e-library services in university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The study obtained a sample of 618 academic librarians and library officers, and employed descriptive and inferential statistical tools to establish that both information culture and organisational structure significantly enhanced user satisfaction with e-library services. This study is closely aligned with the present research in terms of the methodological approach, but differs in context as the current study examines satisfaction from the users' standpoint and not library personnel.

Notwithstanding the above, Onwueke, Olise, and Suleiman (2022) explored the concept of preservation practices which is an element of information culture and analyses its relationship with user satisfaction within Oko Polytechnic Library in Anambra State. Surveying 20 staff members, they found that users preferred well-preserved information in both digital and physical forms. They also identified challenges such as inadequate funding and insufficient preservation equipment. Although the study highlights the importance of information handling practices in enhancing user satisfaction, its small sample size, polytechnic context, and staff-focused population limit its generalisability to university users in states of South-South Nigeria.

From a broader organisational perspective, Peter (2024) conducted a systematic literature review to examine the role of information culture in effective records management and operational efficiency across organisational contexts. Reviewing 35 peer-reviewed articles published between 1993 and 2024, the study concluded that strong information culture enhances organisational decision-making, efficiency, and service delivery. While the findings underscore the strategic importance of information culture, the study's methodological orientation and focus on organisations more broadly differ from the empirical user-based focus of the present study.

Furthermore, Aderelolu and Olawale (2023) examined information culture and technology-use factors influencing evidence-based practice in university libraries in South-West Nigeria. Using a survey of 226 professional librarians, their findings indicated that both information culture and technology utilisation significantly enhanced librarians' capacity for evidence-based service delivery. Although the study aligns with the present research in exploring information culture and technology-related variables, its population (professional librarians) and regional scope differ markedly from the current study that applies a correlational approach and focuses on registered library users in Southern Delta University, Ozoro, a university situated in South-South Nigeria.

2.5 Literature Gap

The existing literature consistently demonstrates that information culture affects organisational performance, service delivery, and user satisfaction across varying contexts. However, notable gaps persist. Many studies have been conducted outside Nigeria or in other Nigerian regions, have focused predominantly on library staff rather than users. Few empirical studies have explored the direct influence of information culture on library users' satisfaction within the

university library polytechnic context in parts of Nigeria, but not in Southern Delta University, Ozoro – Delta State, Nigeria.

The present study addresses these gaps by examining how changes in information culture influence satisfaction among registered users of university libraries in Southern Delta University, thereby contributing context-specific empirical evidence to the broader discourse on change management in academic libraries.

3.0 Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the influence of demographic factors on the promotion of electronic information resources among librarians in state universities in Delta State, Nigeria. The design was deemed suitable because it facilitates the collection of quantitative data and supports the examination of relationships among variables within a defined population (Jeroh, 2019; Jeroh, Iruoma & Adindu, 2023; Anie & Jeroh, 2025). The study's population comprised 4,251 registered library users for the 2024/2025 academic session. Using the Cochran's formula with finite population correction, a sample size of 353 respondents was obtained and selection for inclusion as participant was done using the simple random sampling approach. Data were collected through a validated, structured questionnaire, which was administered to the sampled participants. The retrieved data were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. To test the study's hypothesis, the correlation analysis method was employed at the 0.05 level of significance.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Analysis of Respondents' Demographic Data

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	202	57.22
Female	151	42.78
Total	353	100.00

Level of Study	Frequency	Percentage
100 Level	49	13.88
200 Level	132	37.39
300 Level	54	15.30
400 Level	118	33.43
Total	353	100.00

Self-Rated Digital Literacy	Frequency	Percentage
Low	0	0.00
Moderate	121	34.28
High	178	50.42

Very High	54	15.30
Total	353	100.00

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 1 presents a summary of the gender distribution of the respondents. Accordingly, it is observed that male respondents (57.22%) constituted a higher proportion of the sample compared to female respondents (42.78%). This suggests that male students make up a slightly larger share of the registered library users who participated in the study. The gender difference is moderate and indicates a fairly balanced but male-leaning population. This balance is beneficial, as it allows the study to capture perspectives across gender groups in assessing how information culture correlates with library users' satisfaction.

In addition, with respect to the distribution across levels of study, the results presented in the table indicate that the 200-level students formed the largest group (37.39%), followed by 400-level students (33.43%). In contrast, 100-level (13.88%) and 300-level students (15.30%) represented smaller proportions. This pattern suggests that there is a greater library engagement among intermediate and final-year students. This may be likely due to increased academic workload and research needs. Also, there is a lower representation of 100-level students, which may indicate limited exposure to library resources or ongoing orientation processes. Overall, this distribution supports the expectation that library patronage increases as students advance academically.

With respect to digital literacy profile of respondents, one could observe that no respondent rated themselves as having low digital literacy (0%); an indication that the digital literacy profile of respondents is notably strong with 50.42% rated to have high digital literacy, 34.28% moderate digital literacy and 15.30% having very high level of digital literacy. Combined, nearly all respondents ($\approx 100\%$) rated themselves at moderate to very high digital literacy levels. This indicates that the population possesses the technological skills necessary to engage with digital resources of the library.

4.2 Analysis of Questionnaire Items

Table 2: Analysis of Responses to Items on Change in Information Culture

Item Code	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
CIC1	Library staff encourage users to use digital resources.	4.960	0.279	Strongly Agree
CIC2	The library actively promotes digital services.	4.598	0.53	Strongly Agree
CIC3	Staff show openness toward new information technologies.	4.479	0.539	Strongly Agree
CIC4	Library policies support digital resource usage.	4.597	0.53	Strongly Agree
CIC5	Staff share updates and information about e-resources.	4.646	0.524	Strongly Agree
CIC6	The library provides training/orientation on e-resources.	4.479	0.539	Strongly Agree
CIC7	Management supports digital transformation efforts.	4.598	0.53	Strongly Agree
CIC8	Users' feedback is used to improve digital services.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree
CIC9	Communication about service changes is clear and regular.	4.544	0.542	Strongly Agree
CIC10	Staff efforts in adopting digital services are encouraged.	4.544	0.542	Strongly Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 presents the results of the analysis of the Change in Information Culture (CIC) constructs among library users at Southern Delta University, Ozoro. Ten questionnaire items measured users' perceptions of how the library promotes, supports, and communicates digital transformation initiatives. Mean scores and standard deviations were used to determine the central tendencies and variability of responses.

As observed, analysis of the CIC items shows consistently high mean scores, ranging from 4.479 to 4.960, indicating that respondents overwhelmingly agree that the library demonstrates strong commitment to fostering a supportive digital information environment. The relatively low standard deviations (0.279 – 0.542) further imply a high level of consensus among respondents.

The highest-rated item, CIC1 (Mean = 4.960, SD = 0.279), shows near-unanimous agreement that library staff actively encourage users to engage with digital resources. This finding highlights the pivotal role of frontline staff in promoting digital literacy and resource use, suggesting that interpersonal engagement remains a critical driver of digital adoption. Similarly, CIC8 (Mean = 4.955, SD = 0.298) demonstrates that users strongly believe their feedback is used to improve digital services. This reinforces the perception of a participatory digital transformation process where user input is valued and integrated into service enhancement.

Items related to the promotion and support of digital services (CIC2, CIC4, and CIC7) all record high mean values above 4.59. These results underscore that the library's managerial and policy frameworks are aligned with digital transformation goals. The high scores reflect a structured and institutionally supported approach to promoting digital services, suggesting a mature digital strategy within the university library system. Communication-related items (CIC5, CIC9, and CIC10) also show strong positive ratings (Means = 4.544 – 4.646). This indicates that the library maintains clear communication about service updates while encouraging staff efforts toward digital adoption. The results imply that the library not only disseminates information effectively but also fosters an internal culture that embraces continuous technological adaptation.

Although CIC3 and CIC6 recorded slightly lower means (4.479 each), they still fall within the "strongly agree" range. This suggests that staff openness to new technologies and the provision of training/orientation on e-resources are perceived positively, though these areas may benefit from further strengthening. This aligns with recent findings that continuous staff training is essential for sustaining digital transformation in academic libraries.

Table 3: Analysis of Responses to Items on Users' Satisfaction

Item Code	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
US1	Library staff encourage users to use digital resources.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree
US2	The library actively promotes digital services.	4.544	0.542	Strongly Agree
US3	Staff show openness toward new information technologies.	4.960	0.279	Strongly Agree
US4	Library policies support digital resource usage.	4.598	0.530	Strongly Agree
US5	Staff share updates and information about e-resources.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree
US6	The library provides training/orientation on e-resources.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree
US7	Management supports digital transformation efforts.	4.960	0.279	Strongly Agree

US8	Users' feedback is used to improve digital services.	4.598	0.530	Strongly Agree
US9	Communication about service changes is clear and regular.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree
US10	Staff efforts in adopting digital services are encouraged.	4.955	0.298	Strongly Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 3 presents the results relating to user satisfaction with library services at Southern Delta University. User satisfaction (US) was assessed using ten items designed to measure users' perceptions of service quality, digital service delivery, staff responsiveness, and institutional support for digital transformation. Means and standard deviations were also computed to determine the intensity and consistency of respondents' ratings.

The results show exceedingly high levels of user satisfaction across all items, with mean scores ranging from 4.544 to 4.960, indicating that respondents generally *strongly agree* that the library's services meet or exceed their expectations. Low standard deviations (0.279–0.542) indicate strong agreement and minimal variability among respondents.

The highest-rated items, US3 (Mean = 4.960, SD = 0.279) and US7 (Mean = 4.960, SD = 0.279), reflect strong user satisfaction with staff openness to new information technologies and management's support for digital transformation efforts. These results suggest that both frontline staff and library leadership play essential roles in shaping positive user experiences. The near-perfect ratings imply that users perceive the library as an environment that embraces innovation and operational modernization. Similarly, items US1, US5, US6, US9, and US10 received extremely high mean scores (4.955), showing strong satisfaction with staff encouragement, communication, e-resource updates, training, and support for digital service adoption. These results indicate that users experience consistent support in navigating digital resources and perceive the library staff as approachable, proactive, and service-oriented.

Institutional dimensions of satisfaction (US4 and US8), each with mean values of 4.598 respectively also received strong approval. Users believe that library policies support digital resource usage and that their feedback is taken seriously to enhance digital services. These results underscore a positive organisational climate where user needs are prioritized and systematically integrated into service improvements.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

Table 4 Pearson r on change in information culture and users' satisfaction in Southern Delta University Main Library.

Sources of variation	N	Change in information culture r	Library users' satisfaction r	Remark
Change in information culture	353	1.00	0.9016*	Strong positive correlation
Library users' satisfaction	353	0.9016*	1.00	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

From Table 4, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between change in information culture and library users' satisfaction is 0.9016, based on a sample of 353 respondents. The asterisk (*) indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the chosen significance level (typically $p < 0.05$); thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0). Therefore, we conclude that change in information culture has a significant positive correlation with library users' satisfaction in Southern Delta University Main Library.

Apparently, going by the findings that a strong and statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.9016$, $p < 0.05$) exist between change in information culture and library users' satisfaction at Southern Delta University Main Library, it becomes obvious that efforts targeted at enhancing library's information culture (such as improved management, organization, accessibility, and dissemination of information) are closely associated with higher levels of user satisfaction. The strong positive relationship aligns with prior studies demonstrating that a proactive and adaptive information culture fosters user engagement and satisfaction (Godwin, Madukoma, & Soyemi, 2021; Fourie & Meyer, 2018). It therefore means that Libraries that prioritize effective information practices, incorporate digital technologies, and actively respond to user feedback tend to create an environment in which users perceive services as efficient, accessible, and valuable, thereby enhancing their satisfaction (Thirupathi, 2024; Ugwuanyi et al., 2022).

From a theoretical perspective, the result supports the Change Management Theory, which posits that organizational adaptability and cultural transformation are critical for improving service outcomes and meeting stakeholders' expectations (Khan & Kamal, 2016; Ali & Anwar, 2021). In this context, the transformation of information culture in the library acts as a critical change management factor, directly influencing how users interact with resources and shaping their satisfaction. Consequently, the study underscores the importance of strategically cultivating a robust information culture within academic libraries as a means of enhancing service quality and sustaining user satisfaction.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the results obtained in the course of this study, it was concluded that change in information culture has a strong and statistically significant positive relationship with library users' satisfaction in Southern Delta University Main Library. This finding indicates that enhancements in the library's information culture (such as improved information management, accessibility, user engagement, and responsiveness to feedback) are largely associated with higher levels of user satisfaction. The results suggest that as the library adopts proactive practices, incorporates modern technologies, and fosters an environment that values timely access to relevant information, users are more likely to perceive services as efficient, effective, and valuable. Consequently, cultivating a robust and adaptive information culture emerges as a critical factor in sustaining user satisfaction and ensuring the continued relevance and effectiveness of academic library services.

In view of the above it is recommended that:

- i. University libraries should foster a proactive information culture by establishing clear policies and norms for managing, sharing, and disseminating information. This includes promoting accountability, transparency, and consistency in information handling to ensure users can access reliable and timely resources.

- ii. Libraries should adopt and maintain modern digital tools, such as integrated library systems (ILS), online databases, digital repositories, and self-service kiosks, to enhance accessibility, efficiency, and convenience for users. A strong technological infrastructure reinforces the benefits of an adaptive information culture.
- iii. Regularly engaging users through surveys, suggestion boxes, focus groups, or digital feedback platforms enables the library to understand user needs, monitor satisfaction, and tailor services accordingly. Acting on user feedback reinforces a culture of responsiveness and accountability.
- iv. Libraries should establish mechanisms to regularly assess the effectiveness of their information culture initiatives and their impact on user satisfaction. Periodic evaluation allows for timely improvements and ensures services evolve with changing user expectations.

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